
THE REALISATION OF THE COGNITIVE APPROACH TO CONCEPTUAL METAPHORS

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Abstract

The high pragmatic potential of conceptual metaphors is due to their suggestive and estimated load. The use of laconic metaphorical expression allows the author not only to designate a certain micro-event, but also to express his assessment, which is largely implicit and which can change the attitude of the audience towards a real event.

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The modern cognitive approach to metaphor proceeds from the understanding of metaphor as the main thinking process, as a way of cognizing and structuring the world and as a means of influencing the consciousness and emotional world of the addressee. George Lakoff notes that the problems with traditional theories of the metaphor are in the fact that metaphors were constantly considered only as a linguistic phenomenon, and not as a phenomenon related to all human thinking [1, pp 3-4]. That is, metaphors are not limited by our speech, but exist in our daily lives, in our thinking and actions. Metaphors help us to understand and analyze what is happening around us. This approach allows us to finally bring the metaphor beyond the linguistic system and explore it as a phenomenon of interaction between thinking, language and culture.

Lakoff and Johnson explain that "the essence of metaphor is the understanding and experience of one kind of thing in terms of another". Metaphors, according to these authors, govern our thoughts, structure our understandings, and thus provide for how we conceptualize and live our lives [2, p 5]. In their opinion, abstract things are easier to understand with the help of more specific terms. For example, TIME is an abstract concept, which is easier to understand with the help of a more specific concept MONEY. This conceptual metaphor is reflected in a variety of linguistic expressions in English: You're *wasting* my time. How do you *spend* your time these days? I've *invested* a lot of time in her. Do you have much time *left*? TIME IS MONEY, is a metaphorical concept, "since we are using our everyday experiences with money, limited resources, and valuable commodities to conceptualize time" [2, p 30]. The conceptual metaphors are so densely embedded in people's consciousness and become so familiar that they are often not recognized as metaphors.

Another important thought suggested by Lakoff and Johnson is that much of the human conceptual system is based on spatial orientation. 'Orientational metaphors' organize a whole system of concepts with respect to one another and, most of them, have to do with spatial orientation: *up-down, in-out, front-back, on-off, deep-shallow, central-peripheral* [2, p. 35]. The point is that, orientational metaphors do not define one concept in terms of another, but organize the entire system of concepts in relation to each other: "happy is up" – the fact that the concept "happy is oriented up" leads to such English expressions as "I'm feeling up today". Orientational metaphors are based on the physical and

cultural experience of a person. For example, the physical basis of the metaphor is CONSCIOUS IS UP; UNCONSCIOUS IS DOWN (e.g.: Wake up, I'm up already; he fell asleep) is that people and most animals sleep lying down and get up when they wake up.

The next group of metaphors, namely ontological metaphors, serves different purposes and the various types of metaphors reflect different aims. Just as the basic experiences of human spatial orientations give rise to orientational metaphors, so our experiences with physical objects (especially our own bodies) provide the basis for an extraordinarily wide variety of ontological metaphors, that is, ways of viewing events, activities, emotions, ideas, etc., as entities and substances [2, p.49].

In the framework of the theory of J. Lakoff and M. Johnson, metaphorization is based on the interaction between knowledge structures - the cognitive structure of the "source domain" and the cognitive structure of the "target domain". As a result of unidirectional metaphorical mapping (metaphorical mapping) from "source domain" to the "target domain" formed by the experience of human interaction with the surrounding world, the elements of the "source sphere" structure a less understandable conceptual "target domain", which is the essence of the cognitive potential of the metaphor. In comparison with the "target domain", the "source domain" is usually intuitively clearer, more specific known through direct physical experience. It is known in more detailed way, it can be easier transferred from one person to another. Scientists explain this theory by the example of the concept LOVE IS A JOURNEY: showing how the conceptual sphere "journey" (source domain) as a result of cognitive processes (mapping) is imposed on the conceptual sphere "love" (target domain). The metaphor "journey is love" does not occur, because physical events are not understood through abstract ones.

Ortega y Gasset summarizes all of the above: "A metaphor serves as an instrument of thought, by means of which we manage to reach the remotest parts of our conceptual field. Objects that are close to us, easily comprehended, open thoughts and give access to distant and elusive concepts. The metaphor lengthens the "arm" of the intellect; its role in logic can be likened to a fishing pole or a rifle" [3, p 71].

Taking into consideration the classification of American researchers, conceptual metaphors are di-

vided into three groups: *structural*, *ontological* and *orientational*. In structural metaphors one concept is understood and expressed in terms of another (e.g.: ARGUMENT IS WAR.) Accordingly, we can have the word combinations: *to attack a weak point in one's argument; to win an argument*. In orientational metaphors concepts are spatially related to each other (e.g.: HAPPINESS IS UP, SADNESS IS DOWN). In addition, the orientational metaphor increases the positive or negative evaluation of the concept. Including the concept in the system of orientational oppositions, orientational metaphor automatically assumes a positive or negative perception of the concepts. For ontological metaphors an abstraction (activity, emotion, idea) is represented as something concrete (an object, substance, container, or person). Ontological metaphors are used for better understanding what is happening, to understand surrounding states and actions. For example, the metaphor THE MIND IS A MACHINE creates a concept of the mind as an effective having an on-off state a level of efficiency, a productive capacity, an internal mechanism, a source of energy, and an operating condition. There are various contexts for such a category. e.g.: *I'm a little rusty today. My mind just isn't operating today. I'm going to pieces*.

To illustrate the considered categories of metaphors, we have analysed the extracts from the sports discourse and presented the following results.

Structural metaphors

Taking into account the frequency of the use of militaristic vocabulary in football reports and the cultural origins of this sport, we can make an assumption that to some extent, football is becoming a sublimation of hostilities. "Football is war" metaphor is crucial one or verbal organization of the prepared football reportage and for sports discourse in general. This metaphorical model comes to the fore in the English language [4]. (*to beat the team; to come down to a straight fight; to battle one's way through; to be a classic encounter*). We would like to especially highlight the metaphor "blitzkrieg", which becomes an element of the text compression. It describes a very specific situation: the player goes to the game with the setup to suppress the opponent, to decide the outcome of the match using some advantage. A successful play is the product of good work of a mechanism, unsuccessful play is the result of technical problems. This way we come to the metaphor "team is a mechanism".

Ontological metaphors

According to Lakoff and Johnson, in English, a dispute can be metaphorically realized in terms of moving along a path. It is logical to assume that the metaphor of the path is reflected in sports discourse. Therefore, we can offer the metaphor "play is a journey". The teleological evaluation of the event involves moving towards the goal. To achieve the result, the team goes through a certain path. The football field has a certain size. Thus, players act in the given spatial and time frames. However, one of the important elements of the sport is its unpredictability. Going to the goal involves obstacles on the way. (*to hit a fiercely struck cross right into the path of team mate; to find the shortest route to the gates*).

Oriental metaphors

It is impossible to speak about what is happening on the football field without moving forward and backward, up and down. For football is typical that players enter the field and leave it, for example, when sent off or substituted. The main tool of the player is their own body, which they expose to different contacts and actions [5]. On the other hand, orientational metaphors specify the futility of football, from home gates to opponents' ones, from one sideline to another. (*to be eight matches ahead and ten points behind; to go top/to be on top and to go down/to turn down*).

Thus, we have come to the conclusion that a metaphor, regardless of the type, plays an essential role in categorizing and maintaining the integrity of the constantly evolving and changing linguistic view of the world. It covers the whole sphere of human experience and the physical world.

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